

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS OF STOCHASTIC EFFECTIVE PROPERTIES FOR POLYMER-BASED COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

The main aim of this work is a computer simulation of the effective properties for the polymer-based composites reinforced with the carbon black or silica nano-particles. Contrary to the general formulas available in the homogenization theory addressed to the micro-macro transitions in the composites [1], now experimental results for the specific compositions of the matrix and reinforcing particles are necessary to build up the new additional mathematical models. Further, we study the influence of stochastic fluctuations of the reinforcing particles volumetric ratio on the overall effective properties using the stochastic perturbation technique implemented into the computer algebra system MAPLE. This study may have a paramount importance in industrial applications because of the very realistic nonlinear constitutive models and final probabilistic moments functions of the homogenized materials, especially in the reliability analysis.

2 Theoretical homogenization model

As it is known from the homogenization method history, one of the dimensionless techniques leading to the description of the effective parameters is the following relation describing the shear modulus [3]:

$$G^{(eff)} = f G_0, \quad (1)$$

where G_0 stands for the virgin, unreinforced material and f means the coefficient of this parameter increase, related to the reinforcement portion into the final mixture. A particular characterization of this coefficient strongly depends on the type of the reinforcement (long or short fibers, reinforcing particles, arrangement of this reinforcement etc.) [2]. It is not necessary to underline that the effective nonlinear behavior of many, both traditional and nano composites, needs much more sophisticated techniques based usually

on the computer analysis using the Finite Element Method. Let us note also that elastomers are some specific composite materials, where usually more than two components are analyzed – some interface layers are inserted also between them (as Sticky Hard (SH) and Glassy Hard (GH) layers). We analyze here the homogenization rules under the stress-softening behavior, where the cluster size ξ is a deformation-dependent quantity $\xi = \xi(E)$ with E being a scalar deformation related explicitly to the first strain tensor invariant. The function $\xi = \xi(E)$ is usually determined empirically and it results in the following formulas describing the coefficient f varying together with the strain level changes [3]:

- the exponential cluster breakdown

$$f(E) = X_\infty + (X_0 - X_\infty) \exp(-\alpha E) \quad (2)$$

and

- the power-law cluster breakdown

$$f(E) = X_\infty + (X_0 - X_\infty)(1 + E)^{-\nu}. \quad (3)$$

The following notation is employed here

$$X_\infty = 1 + C \left(\frac{\xi_0}{b} \right)^{d_w - d_f} \varphi^{\frac{2}{3 - d_f}}, \quad (4,5)$$

$$X_0 = 1 + C \varphi^{\frac{2}{3 - d_f}},$$

where $C \in \mathfrak{R}$ and d_w is the fractal dimension representing the displacement of the particle from its original position. Because ξ_0 stands for the initial value of the parameter ξ , one can rewrite eqn (5) as

$$X_0 = 1 + C \Xi^{d_w - d_f} \varphi^{\frac{2}{3 - d_f}}. \quad (6)$$

3 Probabilistic background

The generalized given order stochastic perturbation technique based on the Taylor series expansion with random coefficients is employed. To provide this formulation let us denote the random variable of the

problem by $b(\omega)$ and its probability density as $g(b)$. The central m th probabilistic moment may be expressed as

$$\mu_m(b) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} (b - E[b])^m g(b) db. \quad (7)$$

The coefficient of variation, asymmetry and flatness are introduced in the form

$$\alpha(b) = \frac{\sqrt{\mu_2(b)}}{E[b]}, \beta(b) = \frac{\mu_3(b)}{\sigma^3(b)}, \gamma(b) = \frac{\mu_4(b)}{\sigma^4(b)}. \quad (8)$$

According to the main philosophy of this method, all functions in the basic deterministic problem (heat conductivity, heat capacity, temperature and its gradient as well as the material density) are expressed similarly to the following finite expansion of a random function $G(b)$

$$G(b) = G^0(b) + \dots + \frac{1}{n!} \varepsilon^n \frac{\partial^n G}{\partial b^n} \Delta b^n, \quad (9)$$

where ε is a given small perturbation parameter and the n th order variation is given as follows:

$$\varepsilon^n \Delta b^n = (\delta b)^n = \varepsilon^n (b - b^0)^n. \quad (10)$$

Using this expansion one may derive the expected values exactly from the definition as

$$E[G(b)] = G^0(b^0) + \sum_{m=1}^n \frac{1}{(2m)!} \varepsilon^{2m} \frac{\partial^{2m} G(b)}{\partial b^{2m}} \mu_{2m}(b) \quad (11)$$

for any natural m ; μ_{2m} is the central probabilistic moment of $2m$ th order and analogously one derives the higher probabilistic moments. Usually, according to some previous convergence studies we may limit this expansion-type approximation to the 10 th order. As one may suppose, the higher order moments we need to compute, the higher order perturbations need to be included into all formulas, so that the complexity of the computational model grows non-proportionally together with the precision and the range of the output information needed. This method may be applied to determine $G^{(eff)}(\omega)$ - through the differentiation of both components in the R.H.S. of eqn (1) until the given n th order

$$\frac{\partial^n G^{(eff)}}{\partial b^n} = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} \frac{\partial^k f}{\partial b^k} \frac{\partial^{n-k} G_0}{\partial b^{n-k}} \quad (12)$$

Engineering practice in many cases leads to the conclusion that the initial values of mechanical parameters decrease stochastically together with the

time being. As far as some periodic measurements are available, one can approximate in some way those stochastic processes moments, however a posteriori analysis is not convenient considering the reliability of designed structures and materials. This stochasticity does not need result from the cyclic fatigue loading but may reflect some unpredictable structural accidents, aggressive environmental influences etc. This problem may be also considered in the context of the homogenization method, where the additional formula for effective parameters may include some stochastic processes. Considering above one may suppose, for instance, the scalar strain variable E as such a process, i.e.

$$E(\omega, t) = E^0(\omega) + \dot{E}(\omega)t \quad (13)$$

where superscript 0 denotes here the initial random distribution of the given parameter and dotted quantities stand for the random variations of those parameters (measured in years). From the stochastic point of view it is somewhat similar to the Langevin equation approach, where Gaussian fluctuating white noise was applied. It is further assumed that all aforementioned random variables are Gaussian and their first two moments are given; the goal would be to find the basic moments of the process $f(\omega, t)$ to be included in some stochastic counterpart of eqn (1). The plus sign in eqn (13) suggests that the strain measure with some uncertainty should increase with time according to some initially unpredictable deformations; introduction of higher order polynomial is also possible here and does not lead to significant computational difficulty. A determination of the first two moments of the aging process is analytical, where

$$E[E(\omega, t)] = E[E^0(\omega)] + E[\dot{E}(\omega)]t \quad (14)$$

and

$$Var(E(\omega, t)) = Var(E^0(\omega, t)) + Var(\dot{E}(\omega, t))t^2. \quad (15)$$

Then four input parameters are needed to provide the analysis for stochastic ageing of any of the models presented above; the additional computational analysis is performed with respect to the exponential and power-law cluster breakdown models and we adopt the following data: $E[E_0] = 3$, $E[\dot{E}] = 0.03 \text{ year}^{-1}$, $Var(E_0) = (0.01 E[E_0])^2$, $Var(\dot{E}) = (0.01 E[\dot{E}])^2$. Using this data we provide

probabilistic analysis, where first two moments are dependent on E as well as stochastic model, where time fluctuations are noticed.

4 Computational experiments

The probabilistic coefficients for the exponential (Figs. 1-2) and for the power-law (Figs. 3-4) cluster breakdowns are contrasted, where the overall strain measure E is the Gaussian input variable. The results presented are obtained in the system MAPLE using new implementation of the stochastic perturbation approach [2]. One may find that all the expected values decrease together with an increase of an expectation of E . The coefficient of variation $\alpha(f)$ increases monotonously from 0 (for $E \cong 0$) to some maximum value and then, start to monotonously decrease with maximum dispersion obtained for 60% of the carbon black. The expected values for the power-law cluster breakdown are shown in Fig. 3 – they decrease together with the expectation of the strain measure E and the larger reinforcement volume, the larger expectation $E[f]$. The coefficients of variation given in Fig. 4 are similar to the previous case (cf. Fig. 2) but for some specific combinations of the input parameters they do not have a local maximum and increase for the entire domain of the parameter E . Further we analyze the time fluctuations of the expected values $E[f]$ in Fig. 5 and the additional coefficients of variation $\alpha(f)$ in Fig. 6 reflecting the composite ageing. We notice those variations for 40 and 60% reinforcement by the silica and the carbon black nanoparticles.

Fig. 1. Expected values for the exponential cluster breakdown to the scalar variable E

Fig. 2. Coefficients of variation for exponential cluster breakdown to the scalar variable E

Fig. 3. Expected values for the power-law cluster breakdown to the scalar variable E

Fig. 4. Coefficients of variation for power-law cluster breakdown to the scalar variable E

Fig. 5. Expected values time fluctuations for the exponential cluster breakdown

Fig. 6. The coefficients of variation time fluctuations for the exponential cluster

A general observation is that all the characteristics decrease together with a time increment, not only the expected value. The elastomer shear modulus become closer to the matrix rather together with the time being and the random distribution of the output coefficient f converges with time to the Gaussian one, however the coefficient of variation also tends to 0 (for 60% silica at least). The interrelations between different elastomers are inverse for expectations and variation coefficients – larger values are obtained for carbon black than for the silica (for $E(f)$) and the higher volumetric ratio (in percents), the higher values of the probabilistic characteristics. The coefficient of variation exhibits

exactly the opposite interrelations – higher values are typical for silica reinforcement and for smaller amount of the reinforcing particles in the elastomer specimen. Let us finally note that for 40% silica the expected value of the reinforcement coefficient f becomes smaller than 1 after almost 25 years of such a stochastic ageing.

4 Concluding remarks

Computational technique presented here allows for a comparison of various homogenization methods for the elastomers reinforced with the nanoparticles in terms of parameter variability, sensitivity gradients as well as the resulting probabilistic moments. The most interesting result is in the overall decrease of the probabilistic moments for the process $f(\omega;t)$ together with time during stochastic ageing of the elastomer specimen defined as the stochastic increase of the general strain measure E . Let us mention for further applications that an application of the non-Gaussian variables (and processes) is also possible in this model. The results of probabilistic modeling and stochastic analysis may be very useful in stochastic reliability analysis of the tires, where homogenization methods presented above may significantly simplify the computational FEM model. On the other hand, one may use the stochastic perturbation technique applied here together with the LEM or EPFM approaches to provide a comparison against the statistical results obtained during the basic impact tests.

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